

Valve: Heap Abstraction via Early-Confluent Object Merging for Pointer Analysis (Artifact Document)

Anonymous

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1 Introduction

Our accompanying paper presents VALVE, a heap abstraction for pointer analysis that improves analysis efficiency while preserving most of its precision.

This artifact contains the implementation of VALVE and the scripts required to reproduce the experimental results reported in the paper. In particular, it supports reproducing the following results:

- *Section 5.2, Table 1.* Precision and efficiency statistics of VALVE-enhanced pointer analysis using modern selective context-sensitivity techniques ZIPPER^e and MOON.
- *Section 5.3, Table 2.* Precision and efficiency statistics of VALVE-enhanced pointer analysis using CUT-SHORTCUT.
- *Section 5.4, Figure 10 & 11.* Statistics characterizing the heaps produced by VALVE and MAHJONG.

Before reproducing these results, we first describe how to set up the artifact and perform a quick sanity check.

2 Getting Started

2.1 Basic Requirements

- *Hardware.* In our paper, all experiments were conducted on a machine equipped with an Intel Xeon 2.30 GHz CPU using 256 GB of memory with 8 threads. Since pointer analysis can be very memory-consuming, using a machine with a smaller memory may cause some analyses to be slower or even crash. For machine with limited resource, we recommend you concentrate on (relatively) smaller benchmarks (e.g., findbugs and checkstyle). Also note that the results concerning the execution time of analysis may vary in different running environments.
- *Environment.* To simplify the setup of our artifact, we have provided a Docker image that includes the fully configured evaluation environment. Hence, the only requirement is to have Docker installed on your machine. Our Docker image has been tested on Ubuntu 24.04, and we recommend using Linux for compatibility.

2.2 Setting Up the Artifact

1. *Install Docker.* Install Docker for your operating system by following the instructions at: <https://docs.docker.com/get-started/get-docker/>. If Docker is already installed, you may skip this step.
2. *Load the Docker image.* After installing Docker, load the provided docker image with the following command:

```
bash
$ docker load < valve-artifact.tar.gz
```

This step may take several minutes due to the size of the image.

3. *Create directory for results.* Once loaded, create a directory for storing the results produced by pointer analysis.

```
bash
$ mkdir results
```

The total disk space required for storing all the results is approximately 16 GB. We recommend ensuring 20 GB of storage.

4. *Launch a container from the image.* To launch the loaded container `valve-artifact:oops1a2026` with a name, run the following commands:

```
bash
$ docker run \
  --name valve \
  --mount type=bind,source="$(pwd)/results",target="/artifact/results" \
  -ti valve-artifact:oops1a2026
```

This command opens an interactive shell inside the container. To exit the container, use the command `exit` or press `Ctrl-d`.

Notes on compatibility. This command is compatible with a POSIX compatible shell (e.g., `bash`, `zsh`, `fish`). It won't work in Windows `cmd` or `PowerShell`, due to the use of `$(pwd)` in `--mount`.

Here, `$(pwd)` simply means the *current working directory*. If you don't want to mount, remove `--mount` (output will be lost after exit), or replace `$(pwd)` with an absolute path to the `results` directory created in the previous step.

2.3 Contents in the Artifact

After launching the container, you will be placed in the `/artifact` directory. You can confirm this and inspect the artifact contents by running:

```
bash
$ pwd && ls
```

Unless otherwise noted, all commands in this document should be executed from this directory.

The directory contains:

- `benchmarks/`: all benchmarks used in our evaluation.
- `output/`: intermediate outputs of the pointer analysis.
- `results/`: all raw evaluation results. Outputs generated by subsequent executions will be stored here.
- `scripts/`: easy-to-use scripts for running analyses and collecting the results reported in the paper.
- `tai-e/`: the implementation of VALVE, together with all other techniques used in our evaluation (MAHJONG, ZIPPER^e, MOON, and CUT-SHORTCUT), all built on top of the TAI-E analysis framework.

2.4 Sanity Check

The artifact evaluates several pointer-analysis configurations implemented in TAI-E, which is already compiled and installed in the Docker image. To verify that everything works correctly, we recommend the following two-step sanity check. First, run:

```
bash

$ python -m scripts.run --help

usage: run.py [-h] [--benchmark BENCHMARK [BENCHMARK ...]]
             [--analysis ANALYSIS [ANALYSIS ...]]
             [--rounds ROUNDS]
             [--memory MEMORY]
             [--threads THREADS]
             ...

Run Tai-e pointer analysis for specific configurations and benchmarks
...
```

This command should print usage information and examples for the evaluation script. You do not need to understand every option at this point, but you may refer back to this help message later if needed.

Next, run a quick context-insensitive analysis on one of the smallest benchmarks, findbugs-3.0:

```
bash

$ python -m scripts.run \
    --analysis ci --benchmark findbugs-3.0 \
    --memory 8G --threads 8
```

For readability, we break the command into multiple lines. This command is interpreted as:

1. Run the analysis
2. using ci (context insensitivity with ALLOC)
3. on benchmark findbugs-3.0
4. with 8 GB of memory, using 8 threads.

The analysis should complete within several seconds. When finished, you should see output similar to the following (with build information omitted for brevity):

```
bash

Running round 1
Total configurations to run: 1
=====
[1/1] Running findbugs-3.0
  Context-sensitivity: ci
  Advanced technique: ci
  Memory: 8G, Threads: 8
End running round 1
=====
Benchmark execution completed!
```

The output of this run will be written to: `/artifact/results/round1/ci-null-findbugs-3.0/tai-e.log`. You can inspect it using:

```
bash

$ cat /artifact/results/round1/ci-null-findbugs-3.0/tai-e.log
```

The log should look similar to the following (with irrelevant lines omitted):

```
bash

Analyzing findbugs-3.0
...
[Pointer analysis] elapsed time: 2.57s
----- Pointer analysis statistics: -----
...
#call graph edges:          10,7446 (insens) / 10,7446 (sens)
-----

pta finishes, elapsed time: 3.64s
may-fail-cast starts ...
#may-fail-cast: found 3370 in 5802 reachable relevant Stmts
#may-fail-cast: found 1537 in 1695 reachable relevant Stmts (app)
may-fail-cast finishes, elapsed time: 0.03s
...
thread-escape starts ...
#thread-escape: found 5752 out of 9591 objects
thread-escape finishes, elapsed time: 0.15s
mod-ref starts ...
#mod-ref: found 30745135 objects in 17292 methods
mod-ref finishes, elapsed time: 1.27s
Tai-e finishes, elapsed time: 6.82s
```

If you obtain output of this form, the artifact is set up correctly.

3 Step-by-Step Instructions

This section explains how to reproduce the main experimental results reported in the paper.

Notes on Analysis Time and Rounds. Running all the analyses on all the benchmarks is time-consuming. In our experimental settings, a single round of execution of all the analyses on all the benchmarks took 66 hours, and we ran 3 such rounds to report the average. For convenience, we provided an option `--rounds` to specify how many rounds will be executed (using `scripts.run`) and the results of how many rounds will be averaged (using `scripts.collect`). By default, this option is set to 1.

3.1 Reproducing Table 1 (RQ1)

Table 1 compares VALVE and MAHJONG when used together with ZIPPER^e and MOON.

To reproduce Table 1, the following command executes *all* the analyses for *all* the benchmarks:

```
bash

$ python -m scripts.run \
    --analysis all --benchmark all \
    --memory 256G --threads 8
```

To focus on specific analyses on specific benchmarks, use the following command to display all the choices for analyses and benchmarks:

```
bash
```

```
$ python -m scripts.run --list
```

and then run the following command to run specific analyses (e.g., VALVE and MAHJONG with ZIPPER^e) for specific benchmarks (e.g., findbugs-3.0 and checkstyle):

```
bash
```

```
$ python -m scripts.run \  
  --analysis MZ VZ \  
  --benchmark findbugs-3.0 checkstyle \  
  --memory 256G --threads 8
```

When the analyses finish, run the following command to reproduce the table:

```
bash
```

```
$ python -m scripts.collect table1
```

The Exceptional Case biojava In our paper, we observe that applying context sensitivity to objects merged by VALVE improves both precision and efficiency for analyzing biojava using VALVE with ZIPPER^e. This result can be reproduced using the dedicated option `-apply-cs-to-merged-objects` in the following command:

```
bash
```

```
$ python -m scripts.run \  
  --apply-cs-to-merged-objects \  
  --analysis VZ --benchmark biojava \  
  --memory 256G --threads 8
```

When the analysis finishes, view the results in `/artifact/results/round1/3-obj-VZ-biojava/tai-e.log`, using the following command:

```
bash
```

```
$ cat /artifact/results/round1/3-obj-VZ-biojava/tai-e.log
```

Average of 3 runs. By default, `scripts.collect` reports the results of a *single round* of execution. To report the results of multiple rounds of executions, use the option `--rounds`:

```
bash
```

```
$ python -m scripts.run \  
  --analysis all --benchmark all \  
  --memory 256G --threads 8 \  
  --rounds 3  
$ python -m scripts.collect table1 \  
  --rounds 3
```

3.2 Reproducing Table 2 (RQ2)

Table 2 compares VALVE and MAHJONG when used together with CUT-SHORTCUT.

To reproduce Table 2, run the following command to obtain the analysis results:

```
bash
$ python -m scripts.run \
  --analysis all --benchmark all \
  --memory 256G --threads 8
```

and then run the following command to reproduce the table:

```
bash
$ python -m scripts.collect table2
```

Average of 3 runs. By default, `scripts.collect` reports the results of a *single round* of execution. To report the results of multiple rounds of executions, use the option `--rounds`:

```
bash
$ python -m scripts.run \
  --analysis all --benchmark all \
  --memory 256G --threads 8 \
  --rounds 3
$ python -m scripts.collect table2 \
  --rounds 3
```

3.3 Reproducing Figure 10 & 11 (RQ3)

Figure 10 & 11 presents a detailed characterization of the heap abstraction produced by VALVE.

Figure 10: The number of objects To reproduce Figure 10, we apply a dedicated option `-dump-merged-objects` to dump the objects merged by heap abstractions after executing the analysis. Run the following command to execute a context-insensitive analysis using VALVE and MAHJONG to dump the objects merged by VALVE and MAHJONG:

```
bash
$ python -m scripts.run \
  --dump-merged-objects \
  --analysis valve mahjong ci --benchmark all \
  --memory 256G --threads 8
```

The raw results for VALVE will reside in `/artifact/results/round1/ci-valve-<BENCHMARK>/tai-e.log`, and the results for MAHJONG will reside in `/artifact/results/round1/ci-mahjong-<BENCHMARK>/tai-e.log`.

For convenience, we provide a script to collect the results for Figure 10, which parses the raw results for each approach on each benchmark, displays the number of objects in the resulting heap, and computes a summarized results (i.e., the average over all benchmarks).

```
bash
$ python -m scripts.collect figure10
```

Figure 11: Equivalence classes of VALVE and MAHJONG To reproduce Figure 11, run the following command to execute a context-insensitive analysis using VALVE and MAHJONG to dump the objects merged by VALVE and MAHJONG:

```
bash
$ python -m scripts.run \
    --dump-merged-objects \
    --analysis valve mahjong ci --benchmark all \
    --memory 256G --threads 8
```

The raw results for VALVE will reside in `/artifact/results/round1/ci-valve-<BENCHMARK>/tai-e.log`, and the results for MAHJONG will reside in `/artifact/results/round1/ci-mahjong-<BENCHMARK>/tai-e.log`. Then collect the results by running:

```
bash
$ python -m scripts.collect figure11
```

This command may take several minutes to complete, due to the substantial number of objects merged by VALVE and MAHJONG. For a better experience, the script displays a progress bar during processing.

When finished, the script reports:

- the number of equivalence classes produced per benchmark by each approach, and
- the average size of the equivalence classes produced per benchmark by each approach,

as well as their averages over all benchmarks.

3.4 Summarizing the Results

We have provided a script to summarize the overall evaluation results via the following command:

```
bash
$ python -m scripts.stats
```

4 Analyzing a New Program

In addition to the benchmarks used in our evaluation, the artifact can also analyze new Java programs packed as JAR files. To analyze a new program, please follow the steps below:

1. Pack the target program as JAR files, including (i) the application itself (for example, `App.jar`), and (ii) all required library JARs (for example, `Lib1.jar` and `Lib2.jar`).
2. Copy the JAR files into `/artifact/benchmarks/` inside the Docker container. For example:

```
bash
$ docker cp App.jar valve:/artifact/benchmarks/
$ docker cp Lib1.jar valve:/artifact/benchmarks/
$ docker cp Lib2.jar valve:/artifact/benchmarks/
...
```

3. Edit `/artifact/benchmarks/benchmark-info.yml` to add the new program. For the simple example above, add a new entry like this:

file

```
newapp: # program name
jdk: 17 # analyzed JDK version
main: com.newapp.Main # main class
apps:
  - App.jar # path to the application JAR
libs:
  - Lib1.jar # path to the first library JAR
  - Lib2.jar # path to the second library JAR
  ...
```

4. Run the analysis using the scripts in /artifact/scripts. For example:

bash

```
$ python -m scripts.run \
  --analysis VZ --benchmark newapp \
  --memory 256G --threads 8
```

As with the provided benchmarks, the results will be written to a log file. You can inspect the output with:

bash

```
$ cat /artifact/results/round1/3-obj-VZ-newapp/tai-e.log
```